

BENEFITS AND BARRIERS OF HUMAN RESOURCE INFORMATION SYSTEM IN BHEL, TIRUCHY, TAMILNADU STATE

Dr. L. Manivannan* & R. S. Jeyasakthivel Rajkumar**

* Associate Professor, Erode Arts College, Erode, Tamilnadu

** Research Scholar, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore, Tamilnadu

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Abstract:

An organization success mainly depends upon the effective use of the valuable human resources. The human resources, treated as the strategic assets, make the sustained competitive advantage and outperforming the rivals. The purpose of the research paper is to check the benefits and the barriers of the human resource information system (HRIS) in the BHEL (Bharat Heavy Electrical Limited), Tiruchy. Based on the earlier studies, the researcher has constructed a questionnaire included the benefits and the eight barrier factors. The select sixty respondents of the study have given their replies through the electronic mail. This study has analysed the research questions with the four-point scale and the percentage analysis. The main findings of the study have revealed that the paperwork reduction, the data control improvement, the quick response, the access to information, the manpower reduction, the fewer errors, the streamline of the process, and the save time are the main benefits of the HRIS implementation in the organization, but a lack of funds, an inadequate knowledge, a lack of expertise, a lack of cooperation, the network problem, a lack of staff, the technical problem and the time consumption are some of the barriers to the HRIS implementation. The current study has attempted to get a greater understanding of the HRIS benefits and barriers and help gain some insights into the HRIS performance and the application in the BHEL. This could help in improving the effectiveness of the HRIS in the BHEL, Tiruchy.

Key Words: BHEL, HRIS & HR

Introduction:

The technological development has forced the organizations to adopt the new technology to survive in the competitive market. Over the last decade; the information system has become important for all the public sector organizations use it as a tool to manage the human resource functions successfully. The human resource information system is an important technology developed with the information technology as a human resource management function. It is a technology-based system used to acquire, store, manipulate, analyse, retrieve, and distribute the information about an organization human resources that consist of the salary and payroll, the compensation, the leave, the performance appraisals, the accidents, the retirement employee benefits, etc. It decreases the cost of administrative works, increasing the productivity, the shortening the time of response, the improving the decision-making, and the developing the customer service quality. It is a connection between the HR management and the information technology (IT). It is not concentrated on the HR management issues only, but also on the organizational goals. Therefore, the HRIS records the files to the computer.

Literature Review:

Raija & Hlonen (2009) have described the use of information system in the financial administration, the human resource management and the social welfare and explored the role of information system in decision-making in the public sector and pointed out that the lack of interoperability between the legacy systems and the new information systems are a huge problem in the organization.

Matthew & Douglas (2009) have analysed that the information system development in any organization is characterized by the multidimensional and often the messy problems to involve the technical organizations and the personal dimensions.

Dr. Karishna & Meena (2010) have identified the various functional areas to which the ICT is deployed for the information administration in the Higher Education Institutions and mentioned that the current level of usage indicates a clear integration of the ICT for the managerial or the information based administration in the higher education institutes.

David et al (2010) have analysed the efficiency of the firm through the samples of the Catalan firms. The efficiency of the firm shows a significant improvement when the human resource practices combine with the uses of the advanced ICT.

Dileep (2010) has indicated that the HRIS integrates the HRM and the information system. The HRIS helps the HR managers do the HR functions in a more effective and systematic way by using the technology and usually being a part of the management information system of the organization that includes the accounting, the production, and the marketing functions.

Kristine & David (2010) have identified that the implementations or the up-gradation of the HRIS has been undertaken with the aim of utilizing the HR management functions and indicated that the barriers

associated with the new and upgraded HRIS acceptance play an important role in shaping the user perception and behaviour.

Rand H. Al-Dmour¹ & Zu'bi M. F. Al-Zu'bi (2014) have indicated that the most frequent applications of the HRIS used in the business organizations in Jordan are "the Employee Records," followed by "the Pay Roll" and "the Recruitment/Selection." This study has shown that the benefits of HRIS include the quicker response time, the more accurate HR information, the reduction of paperwork and the manpower, and the more efficient tracking and controlling and the barriers, the cost implications and an inadequate knowledge in implementing the system.

Sabrina Jahan (2014) has analysed the small corporate houses and the big organizations, failed to realize the benefits of HRIS, and taken hardly any initiative to carry out the system. The author of this study has further identified the lack of management commitment and the high cost of the HRIS introduction, being the major barriers to the success of the HRIS. But, the benefits of the HRIS are more than the limitations mentioned in this study. The author has strongly expressed that the organization, the employees, and the management do realise the benefits from getting the HRIS implemented.

Dr. Shine David, Surbhi Shukla, Shivangi Guptabrina Jahan (2015) have said that the organization's success depends on the effective use of its valuable human resources. Nowadays, every organization treats the human resources as the strategic assets. The HR executives adopt the HRIS to make their organization competitive advantage and outperforming the rivals. The organizations are now adopting the HRIS than ever before for ensuring the effective use of their human resources. But, many challenges and issues keep the organizations deprived of enjoying the benefits of this technology. In this research work, the authors have tried to explore those hurdles based on the responses of the human resource (HR) executives, the employees, who are the frequent use of the HRIS in the organization operating in India. This research work has come across many challenges that impede the effective implementation of HRIS. Finally, they have suggested measurable actions improve the effective HRIS execution.

The Significance of the Study:

The study provides insight into the HRIS implementation in the public sector organization in India. It helps the practitioner have a better understanding of the benefits and barriers to the HRIS implementation.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objective of this study is to explore the barriers that impede the effective implementation of the HRIS in the modern organisations. To materialize the main objective, the study has attempted with the following specific objectives:

- ✓ To find out the HRIS benefits in the BHEL
- ✓ To examine the barriers to the HRIS implementation in the BHEL

Methodology:

Type of Research: This kind of study is the qualitative research that is basically a collection and an analysis and interpretation of data by observing what the public say. Qualitative Research is an exploratory and open-ended, being much more subjective and using the different information collection methods, mainly an individual, an in-depth interview and the focus group. The researcher has conducted this research work by an in-depth interview with a small group of numbers.

Data Sources: The researcher has selected the BHEL as a sample unit for the research study and chosen the simple random sampling method for the choice of respondents. The sample size of this research consists of the 60 respondents irrespective of the age group, involving in the functioning of the Human resource information system.

Data Analysis: The analysis of data is done through the tabulation and percentage.

Age of the Respondents: The respondents' age is an important component shown in the following Table

Table 1: Age of the respondents

S.No	Age of respondents	Frequency	Percentage
1	31-40	40	66.67
2	40 and above	20	33.33
	Total	60	100.00

Table 1 shows respondents' age that is an important element to know their involvement in the HRIS functions. The 66.67 percentages of respondents are in the age between 31 and 40, but the rest of the respondents are in the age group of 40 and above.

Education Level: Education makes the respondents understand the critical and complicated matters with easy. The following Table 2 explains the education level of the respondents in the organisation that they are working.

Table 2: Education Level

S.No	Education level	Frequency	Percentage
1.	Undergraduate	30	50.00
2.	Postgraduate	30	50.00
3.	Others	Nil	-----

	Total	60	100.00
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Table 2 shows the role of education in the use of the HRIS in the organisation. The fifty percent of the respondents are the postgraduates, but 50% the undergraduates.

Work Experience: The experienced employees may produce the results far better than the inexperienced employees produce and being able to complete the work assigned them in a fewer allotted hour with the best quality and avoiding the material wastage. The following Table 3 shows the work experience of the employees in the organisation.

Table 3: Work Experience

S.No	Work Experience	Frequency	Percentage
1	1-2years	15	25
2	3-6 years	30	50
3	7years and more	15	25
	Total	60	100

Table 3 shows the employees work experience calculated by taking the length of service into account. In the total select respondents, the 50% of the employees have the work experience between three and six years. The 25% of the employees work experience in their field is from one to two years and the remaining the 25%, seven years and more.

Benefits of HRIS in BHEL: The following Table 4 shows the benefits of the HRIS according to the opinion of the researcher of this study.

Table 4: Benefits of HRIS in BHEL

S.No	Factor	Division	Frequency	Percentage
1	Reducing Paper work	Agree	17	28.33
		Strongly agree	33	55.00
		Disagree	7	11.67
		Strongly disagree	3	5.00
2	Quick Response	Agree	17	28.33
		Strongly agree	31	51.67
		Disagree	8	13.33
		Strongly disagree	4	6.67
3	Improving the data control	Agree	12	20.00
		Strongly agree	39	65.00
		Disagree	4	6.67
		Strongly disagree	5	8.33
4	Easy Access to information	Agree	14	23.33
		Strongly agree	37	61.67
		Disagree	6	10.00
		Strongly disagree	3	5.00
5	Improving the services	Agree	11	18.33
		Strongly agree	41	68.33
		Disagree	5	8.33
		Strongly disagree	3	5.00
6	Streamlining the process	Agree	23	38.33
		Strongly agree	29	48.33
		Disagree	7	11.67
		Strongly disagree	1	1.67
7	Less errors	Agree	20	33.33
		Strongly agree	25	41.67
		Disagree	9	15.00
		Strongly disagree	6	10.00
8	Reducing the manpower	Agree	18	30.00
		Strongly agree	35	58.33
		Disagree	6	10.00
		Strongly disagree	1	1.67
9	Save the time	Agree	18	30.00
		Strongly agree	36	60.00
		Disagree	5	8.33
		Strongly disagree	1	1.67

10	Enhancing the competitiveness	Agree	16	26.67
		Strongly agree	34	56.67
		Disagree	10	16.67
		Strongly disagree	0	0.00

Table 4 describes the benefits of the HRIS implementation in the BHEL. The researcher of this study has measured the benefit factors through the four-point Licker scale with the select respondents and arranged them in the sequential order. The first benefit factor strongly agreed by the 41 respondents is improving service having the 68.33%; the second, 39, improving data control, 65%; the third, 37, easy access information, 61.67%; the fourth, 36, save time, 60%; the fifth, 35, reducing manpower, 58.33%; the sixth, 36, save time, 60%; the seventh, 33, reducing paperwork, 55%; the eighth, 31, quick response, 51.77%; the ninth, 29, streamlining process, 48.33% and the tenth, 25, less error, 41.67%. A researcher has concluded from the Table 4 analysis that the HRIS improves services and data control, giving information to the management and workers, saving the time, reducing the requiring manpower, enhancing the competitiveness, reducing the paper works, making the response quickly, streamlining the process and decreasing the errors. They are the benefits of the HRIS implementation and at the same time, re-engineering the entire HR functions of the organization.

Problems in Adopting HRIS: The uses of the HRIS in an organization are affected by the various factors, which are highlighted in the following Table 5

Table 5: Problems in adopting HRIS

S.No	Factor	Division	Frequency	Percentage
1	Lack of funds	Agree	9	15.00
		Strongly agree	36	60.00
		Disagree	10	16.67
		Strongly disagree	5	8.33
2	Lack of cooperation	Agree	10	16.67
		Strongly agree	28	46.67
		Disagree	7	11.67
3	Lack of expertise	Strongly disagree	10	16.67
		Agree	15	25.00
		Strongly agree	40	66.67
4	Lack of staff	Disagree	3	5.00
		Strongly disagree	2	3.33
		Agree	15	25.00
		Strongly agree	25	41.67
5	Network Problem	Disagree	17	28.33
		Strongly disagree	3	5.00
		Agree	21	35.00
		Strongly agree	25	41.67
6	Technical Problems	Disagree	4	6.67
		Strongly disagree	10	16.67
		Agree	11	18.33
		Strongly agree	30	50.00
7	Inadequate Knowledge	Disagree	7	11.67
		Strongly disagree	12	20.00
		Agree	19	31.67
		Strongly agree	29	48.33
8	Time Consumption	Disagree	8	13.33
		Strongly disagree	4	6.67
		Agree	10	16.67
		Strongly agree	31	51.67
		Disagree	13	21.67
		Strongly disagree	6	10.00

Table 5 shows the factors affecting the HRIS implementation. From the above Table, the researcher of this study arranges the factors, according to the respondents' opinion. Out of the 60 samples of this study, the 40 respondents have strongly agreed that a lack of expertise is the first cause of the eight select factors in the HRIS implementation; the 36 respondents, a lack of funds, the second; the 31 respondents, the time consumption, the third; the 30 respondents, the technical problems, the fourth; the 29 respondents, a lack of cooperation, the fifth; the 28 respondents, an inadequate knowledge, the sixth and every 25 respondents,

separately, a network problem and a lack of staff, the seventh and the eighth. The above causes mentioned by 60 the respondents of the study are against the tendency of the firm to carry out the HRIS in the BHEL successfully.

Conclusion:

The new technology recently emerged, completely changes the way of conducting /managing/administrating the business. Of late, the HRIS plays a pivotal role in all the organisations. The HRIS role has become strategic. The information available at the right time to the organisation improves the services of the HR department. The BHEL in Tiruchy has not implemented the HRIS fully, but it reduces the need for manpower, saving the time, improving the services and data control and enhancing the competitiveness. At the same time, the HRIS creates some problems in the organisation, namely a lack of expertise, the technical problems, a lack of funds, the time consumption etc.

Actually, the HRIS is a newly implemented system. The employees and the management should understand and streamline the HRIS system that helps the organisation develop the employees' skill and being for the organizations to get the timely information from all the departments. Moreover, some barriers preventing the organisation to carry out the HRIS successfully are a lack of funds, a lack of expertise, etc. Further research about some causes affecting the HRIS implementation properly in the BHEL, Tiruchy may be undertaken.

References:

1. Raija, G., and Hlonen, W.R. (2009), "The evaluation of strategic information systems planning, Information and Management", Vol. 26 pp.327-40.
2. Mathew, J.A. and Douglas, N. (2009), "Strategic information systems planning: applying private sector frameworks in UK public healthcare", London.
3. Kirishnareni, R & Meenakumari, j(2010) "Usage of ICT information administration in Higher education Institution" A study of International journal of environmental science and development vol. 1 no.3
4. David, J., Jelf, G., and Brandes, D. (2010), "Human resource information systems: operational issues and strategic considerations in a global environment". International Journal of Human Resource Management, 7(1): 245-269.
5. Dileep, A. (2010), "Enterprise resource planning: the emerging organizational value systems", Industrial Management & Data Systems, April, 2000, Volume 100, Issue 3, p114-118.
6. Kristine, C. and David, C. H. (2010), "Current Developments in HRM in Australian Organisations", Asia Pacific Journal of Human Resources, 44(2): 132- 152.
7. Rand H. Al-Dmour1 & Zu'bi M. F. Al-Zu'bi (2014) "Factors Motivating and Inhibiting the Practice of HRIS in Business Organizations": An Empirical Analysis International Business Research; Vol. 7, No. 7; pp.139-155
8. Sabrina Jahan (2014) "Human Resource Information System (HRIS): A Theoretical Perspective", Journal of Human Resource and Sustainability Studies, Vol.2 No.2 (2014), Article ID: 46129, 7 pages.
9. Dr. Shine David, Surbhi Shukla, Shivangi Gupta (2015) Barriers in Implementing Human Resource Information System in Organisation", International Journal of Engineering Research and Management (IJERM) ISSN: 2349- 2058, Volume-02, Issue-05, 7pages.